

EDITORIAL MESSAGE**Progress in Physics: 10 Years in Print**

In January, 2015, we celebrate first 10 years of our journal *Progress in Physics*. This is a good time to remember what events led to the idea of the journal, and how the journal was founded.

Ten years ago, in the fall of 2004, CERN Document Server has changed its policy so that it closed its door for all future pre-prints submitted by non-CERN employee. All other persons were advised to submit their papers to Cornell E-Print Archive (known as arXiv.org).

The main problem of this change was that Cornell E-Print Archive only accept papers from people who have a scientific institute affiliation. This policy continues to this day, and is a necessary condition for consideration of papers in almost all modern scientific journals.

This was a serious impact to the scientific community, where so many researchers continue their studies in between short-term grants, or even continue their scientific activity as independent researchers. They all are not affiliated to any scientific institution. So, they all loose their fundamental right to be published in scientific journals.

But it was not always. In already the beginning of the 20th century, every person was able to submit a paper to any scientific journal. And this paper was considered according to its real scientific importance, not the formal degree or scientific institute affiliation of the submitter. Otherwise, many great scientists such as Einstein and others would never have published their scientific works.

However, in the early 20th century, science was a matter of a very few people. With the progress of democracy and improved living mass of the people, in the 1950–1960's, science has become a professional field of activity of hundreds of thousands and even millions of people in the world. Massive investment in research activities have led to the fact that the scientific community is filled with people who do not view science as a search for truth but as “employment”. Many scientific workers speak frankly to each other that we went to the science just in order “to get good income” thus doing some formal activities in the field which is a hard to understand for investors who pay for it all. Such “research staff”, not being burdened with a large intellectual tension of the solution of scientific problems were much more socially active than the real scientists. Therefore, they quickly and systematically took formal positions in the scientific community, including scientific journals. As a matter of fact that they considered real scientists as potentially dangerous persons, who may potentially qualify for their sure and well-paid job positions. To defend themselves, they built a complicate bureaucratic system, where, as Grisha Perelman said very well, no one researcher who is really busy with research will waste so much

time and effort to fill out all the paperwork for a grant. Only familiarity in the editorial board of the scientific journal, or belonging to the “friendly” scientific group gives the opportunity to publish your article.

In this way, the scientific bureaucracy was born. This situation continues in the scientific community until this day.

In this background, CERN Document Server was the solely possibility to publish research papers for the scientists, who are not joined into “groups” or do not belong to “scientific clans”. In the fall of 2004, this window was closed.

It is comical, but even papers authored by Brian Josephson (Nobel Prize in Physics, 1973) were refused by Cornell E-Print Archive. As was claimed the reason was that he has right only to submit articles on his very particular field of physics, and has not rights to submit articles on other field of physics where he “cannot be an expert”.

Correspondence among Josephson and other researchers, who were thinking of the future of the scientific community, has began. In the course of correspondence with Josephson, I met Florentin Smarandache. We both were active CERN E-Print Server users. I looked for another possibility to publish a series of research papers authored by me and Larissa Borissova, my closest colleague and friend. In our common discussion with Florentin, I told him that we must establish a new journal of physics: it is better and easier than to fight for influence in existing journals. Do you like to see this journal in print? — Florentin replied. So, *Progress in Physics* was established by our common power. It was January, 2005.

Then I wrote *Declaration of Academic Freedom*, to fix the fundamental rights and freedoms allowed among the scientific community. This text, known also as *Academic Bill of Rights* is now published in ten languages. All that we do in our journal, is according to the articles of the Bill.

During the first year, we had no many authors and readers. Nevertheless, ten years later, i.e. now, the journal has grown very much. We now have a stable traffic in the range from 25,000 to 35,000 downloaded papers per month, with some peaks in the months when a hot research is published.

Despite some difficulties, the journal is now stable. We allow every person to submit a paper, with the warranty that the submission will be reviewed according only to scientific judgements, independent on the personality of the submitter. Our personnel works on voluntary basis, to keep the author's fee as low as possible. I hope that first 10 years of *Progress in Physics* will be the beginning of the long term life of the journal, among the other respected journal of physics.

Dmitri Rabounski, Editor-in-Chief